

MIRZO ULUG'BEK NOMIDAGI
O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETI
JIZZAX FILIALI

**KOMPYUTER ILMLARI VA
MUHANDISLIK TEXNOLOGIYALARI**

**XALQARO ILMIY-TEXNIK
ANJUMAN MATERIALLARI**

TO'PLAMI

1-QISM

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WAYS TO IMPROVE THE PROCESS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO UNIVERSITY STUDENTS USING ELEMENTS OF MODULAR TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: In accordance with the Federal State Standard of Higher Education, the goal of teaching a foreign language at a university is to develop students' foreign language communicative competence. Particular emphasis on independent work of students determines the transition to technologies that contribute to more effective development of this competence. Modular organization of the process of teaching a foreign language is becoming relevant. The fundamental principles of compiling modular programs are the principles of individualization and differentiation of training.

Keywords: intercultural communication, modular learning technology, pedagogical technology, module.

The purpose of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic, in particular, pedagogical university, is the development of a personality possessing foreign language communicative competence in the process of studying the disciplines "Foreign Language" and "Foreign Language in Professional Activity", i.e. a university graduate must be ready and able to take part in intercultural and professional communication. For the most effective achievement of the learning goals in the current conditions of education in higher education, characterized by an ever-increasing role of independent learning activities of students, it is necessary to focus on the use of modular learning technology.

The idea of modular learning is not new. In the late 80s - early 90s, a new term from the field of technical sciences "bursts" into pedagogical science, namely "module". Since then, they began to talk about the advantages of modular learning in the education system. The word "module" has many meanings in various sciences. As for pedagogical science, here the module is considered an important part of the entire system, without knowledge of which the didactic system does not work. In its content, a module is a complete, logically complete block. In domestic pedagogy, the basics of modular learning are revealed in the works of Palmira Albinovna Yutsevichene [4] and Tatyana Ivanovna Shamova [3], who defined the essence and advantages of modular learning.

The student achieves specific goals of educational and cognitive activity completely independently (or with a certain amount of assistance) in the process of working with the module, working with the individual educational program offered to him, which includes a target lesson plan, an information bank and methodological guidelines for achieving the set didactic goals, and the teacher manages his studies: motivates, organizes, coordinates, consults, controls.

It should be noted that modular training involves strict structuring of educational information, training content and organization of students' work with training units. The module coincides with the subject topic, everything is measured and assessed: assignment, work, attendance at classes, initial, midterm and final control. The learning objectives, tasks and levels of studying the module should be clearly formulated. In modular training, everything should be programmed in advance: the sequence of studying the educational material, the level of its assimilation and control of the quality of assimilation [1].

The essence of modular learning is that the student, with the help of a teacher or independently, achieves individual goals of educational and cognitive activity in the process of working with a module. The student is guided by specific instructions that define:

1. The purpose of mastering the module.
2. Search for educational material (where to find educational material?)
3. Methods of mastering educational information (learn, read and translate, complete an exercise in accordance with the assignment).
4. Checking the correctness of the completed task. Control (various types of tests, written work, reports, presentations) determines the degree of assimilation of the educational material by the student.

Students in the modular approach to learning should know a list of basic concepts, skills and abilities for each specific module, including a quantitative measure of assessing the quality of assimilation of the educational material. Based on this list, questions and learning tasks are compiled, covering all types of work on the module, which are submitted for control after studying the module. As a rule, a test should be the form of control.

The planning stage is also the most important moment. When planning a course (program module), the teacher takes into account the relationship of such factors as the starting level of students, the total amount of time allocated in the curriculum for the course, the amount and complexity of material for assimilation and achievement of the goal, that is, the teacher answers the questions: why to teach? Whom to teach? What to use? How to teach?

The block-modular system of structuring the content of training allows us to look at the educational material as a well-planned, connected and easily adaptable system, which makes it possible in each specific case to build the content of professional training, and consequently, the educational process itself, in maximum accordance with the goals of training, available resources and market needs.

The analysis of the content and structure of foreign language communicative competence of students of non-linguistic specialties, the identified potential of modular training allows us to talk about several conditions that favor the development of foreign language communicative competence by means of modular training. These conditions imply:

- development of a model for the development of students' foreign language competence based on a systemic, competency-based and communication-oriented approach and its implementation in the educational process of the university;
- ensuring the continuity of educational modules and modular programs and their complementarity with respect to special disciplines;
- activation of independent work;
- implementation of a differentiated approach to the development of foreign language competence. It is ensured by the flexible construction of educational modular programs and modules, which include tasks developed in accordance with the students' levels of foreign language competence.

In connection with the tendency to increase the share and importance of independent work, the problem of organizing independent work of students aimed at more effective acquisition of a foreign language comes to the forefront in the design of modular programs. Particular attention in training is shifting from teaching to learning as an independent activity of students. It is important to emphasize that the student's learning is not self-education of an individual at his own request, but a systematic, teacher-controlled independent activity, which in the new conditions becomes predominant.

Thus, the organization of independent work of students in the conditions of block-modular teaching of a foreign language contributes to the emergence of opportunities for the transition to individualized and differentiated training programs, which in turn contributes to an increase in the level of formation of foreign language communicative competence of students of non-linguistic specialties.

The use of the individualization principle in the learning process allows us to take into account the motivation and activity of each student. Taking into account the inclination, life experience, range of interests, emotional sphere, worldview contributes to the emergence of true motivation and internal activity of students in the process of learning a foreign language.

It should be emphasized that modular technology allows to reduce the time of studying the course by 30%.

The above allows us to conclude that the technology of modular learning is not just a pedagogical technology used in teaching students a foreign language, but a necessary condition for mastering a foreign language culture by creating favorable conditions for the development of future specialists as cultural and linguistic individuals who possess highly developed communicative and cultural skills in solving communicative problems.

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ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЧАТ-БОТОВ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются чат-боты с точки зрения их содержательной функции, которую можно использовать в развитии иноязычных речевых умений обучающихся. При этом под чат-ботами с позиции методики преподавания иностранных языков понимается диалоговая обучающая программа, способная на основе заложенных в неё алгоритмов речевого поведения человека развивать иноязычные устные и письменные речевые умения обучающегося посредством поддержания с ним диалога и имитацией человеческой речи. На современном этапе технологического развития мирового сообщества образуются динамичное внедрение технологий искусственного интеллекта в различные сферы жизнедеятельности человека. Это играет важную